

LEXICO-SEMANTIC FEATURES OF SOMATIC UNITS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN THE ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

The relevance of the work is the identification of the national specifics of specific areas of language systems, in the further improvement of methods and techniques for contrastive description of the language. Somatic phraseological units in English and Russian linguistic cultures reflect in their semantics the features of the mentality and traditions characteristic of the representatives of these cultures therefore it is important to identify the linguistic manifestations of these features.

The present goal defined the statement of the following tasks:

1. to study the theoretical material on the topic "the concept of phraseological unit";
2. to study theoretical material on the topic "somatism in phraseology";
3. consider the use of a phraseological unit with the some components in English.

The practical importance lies in the possibility of applying the materials of the research in the practice of translation, language teaching, in a special course in phraseology, geography and intercultural communication.

Phraseology is the science of phraseological units (phraseological units), i.e. about stable combinations of words with complicated semantics that are not formed according to generating structural-semantic models of variable combinations.

Phraseological units (phraseological units) fill in the gaps in the lexical system of the language, which cannot fully provide the name of the (new) aspects of reality known to man, and in many cases are the only designations for objects, properties, states, situations, etc. it should be borne in mind that "the name itself is not only a process of designating a denotation, but also a process of cognition." The formation of phraseological units weakens the contradiction between the needs of thinking and the limited lexical resources of the language. In those cases where a phraseological unit has a lexical synonym, they usually differ in stylistic terms. Phraseology is a treasure trove of language. Phraseological units reflect the history of the people, the originality of their culture and way of life. Phraseologisms often have a clearly national character. along with

purely national phraseological units in English phraseology there are many international phraseological units. The English phraseological fund is a complex conglomeration of original and borrowed phraseological units with a clear predominance of the former. In some phraseological units, archaic elements are preserved - representatives of previous eras.

In phrase formation, the human factor plays a huge role, since the vast majority of phraseological units are associated with a person, with various areas of his activity, the addressee factor is the most important element of communication. In addition, a person seeks to endow objects of the external world, including inanimate ones, with human features. Even S. Bally argued: "The eternal imperfection of the human mind is also manifested in the fact that a person always strives to spiritualize everything that surrounds him. He cannot imagine that nature is dead and soulless; his imagination constantly gives life to inanimate objects, but that's not all: a person constantly ascribes to all objects of the outside world the features and aspirations inherent in his personality. Linguistic anthropomorphism is not a relic of primitive thinking, as some philosophers claim, but a general law of development of the means of nomination in language. The material presented in this book confirms this position. Linguistic anthropomorphism is usually understood as endowing objects and phenomena of inanimate nature, celestial bodies, animals and mythological creatures with human properties.

Phraseological units are highly informative units of the language; they cannot be regarded as "decorations" or "excesses". A similar interpretation of phraseological

units is found in some works and is currently outdated. Phraseological units are one of the linguistic universals, since there are no languages without phraseological units. English phraseology is very rich and has a long history.

Phraseology is an extremely complex phenomenon, the study of which requires its own research method, as well as the use of data from other sciences - lexicology, grammar, stylistics, phonetics, language history, history, philosophy, logic and country studies.

The opinions of linguists on a number of problems of phraseology diverge, and this is quite natural. Nevertheless, an important task of linguists working in the field of phraseology is in the interests of both the theory of phraseology and the practice of teaching foreign languages.

According to N.M. Shansky phraseology is a branch of the science of language that studies the phraseological system in its current state and historical development.

Phraseological phrases are the object of study of phraseology, i.e. stable combinations of words, similar in their reproducibility as ready-made and integral units to words (put on your feet, milk on your lips has not dried up, soul and body, etc.). Thus, phraseology studies both stable combinations of words that are semantically equivalent to a word, and stable combinations of words, and stable combinations of words, which are sentences in a semantic and structural sense, i.e. all reproducible units without exception.

The main task facing phraseology is the knowledge of the phraseological system of the language in its present and history, in its connections and relationships with

vocabulary and word formation, on the one hand, and with grammar, on the other [17]. The term "phraseology" literally means "the doctrine of turns of speech" (from the Greek. phrasis "turnover, expression", logos "concept, doctrine"). Such essentially ambiguous content of the term "phraseology" has survived to this day. This term is used for the name of a section of linguistics that studies all phraseological units, regardless of the nature of their grammatical structure and meaning.

The history of phraseology as a linguistic discipline in Russian linguistics goes back to the works of M.V. Lomonosov, it is known that he collected a number of proverbs, in addition, he believed that "phrases and idioms" should be placed in dictionaries.

At the origins of phraseology are such domestic linguists as F.I. Buslaev, A.A. Shakhmatov, F.F. Fortunatov, M.M. Pokrovsky, A.A. Potebnya, E.D. Polivanov and others. In their works, they analyzed the semantic and grammatical features of stable combinations of words, expressed thoughts about the nature of this stability and reproducibility.

The question of phraseology as a linguistic discipline was first raised by the outstanding Soviet linguist Professor E.D. Polivanov. E.D. Polivanov believed that phraseology would take a separate and stable position, like morphology, phonetics, etc. in the linguistic literature of the future - when our science is devoid of consistent formulation of various problems, there will be random gaps.

Famous works of Academician V.V. Vinogradov laid the foundation for a broad study, arousing interest among domestic philologists in this linguistic object. It was Russian scientists who discovered stable

combinations of words, noted their fixation in the language due to the multiple and stability of the lexical composition and word order, established the presence of changeable and unchangeable combinations of words, noticed the difference between a combination and a compound word.

The modern theory of phraseology is being developed by several groups of researchers. It should be noted that in the field of phraseology research, foreign linguistics lags behind the domestic one. Many of the foreign linguists, dealing with the problem of phraseology, stop only at compiling dictionaries and lists of idioms, but without classification and analysis. In this case, idioms are understood as a special use of certain words, as well as special expressions and turns, which, due to long use in the language, have become frozen stereotypical expressions.

As an independent section of lexicology, phraseology was first identified by S. Balli. Balli first systematized combinations of words in his books "Essay on Stylistics" and "French Stylistics". Balli included a chapter on phraseology in his books on style. In the first book, he singled out four groups of phrases:

- 1) free phrases, i.e. combinations lacking stability, decomposing after their formation;
- 2) habitual combinations, i.e. phrases with a relatively free connection of components, allowing some changes;
- 3) phraseological series, i.e. groups of words in which two adjacent concepts merge almost into one. The stability of these turns is fixed by the primary word usage;

4) phraseological units, i.e. combinations in which words have lost their meaning and express a single indecomposable concept. Such combinations do not allow rearrangement of components. Thus, Bally distinguishes combinations of words according to the degree of stability: combinations in which there is freedom to group components, and combinations that are deprived of such freedom. Bally only sketched these groups, but did not give any detailed description of them.

In recent years, most linguists have come to the conclusion that phraseology is an independent linguistic discipline. The further development of phraseology has stepped far forward thanks to such scientists as V.L. Arkhangelsky, V.P. Zhukov, N.M. Shansky, V.N. Telia, L.I. Roizenzon in Russian phraseology. In English phraseology - N.N. Amosova, A.N. Smirnitsky, A.V. Kunin.

Phraseologism is a phrase reproduced in speech, built on the model of coordinating or subordinating phrases, which has a holistic meaning and is combined with the word.

Phraseologism is endowed with a number of essential, defining features: reproducibility, stability, semantic integrity of meaning, dismemberment of its composition, openness (openness) of the structure.

Reproducibility is regular repetition, renewability in speech of language units of varying degrees of complexity; winged sayings are reproduced (and the smoke of the fatherland is sweet and pleasant for us), proverbs and sayings (you will go further), phraseological combinations (pay attention, get addicted), phraseological units proper (play the fool, squeeze juice), etc.

Idiomaticity is the semantic indecomposability of a phraseological unit in general. Stability is a measure, a degree of semantic unity and indecomposability of components.

Phraseology is the general name for semantically non-free combinations of words that are not produced in speech (as syntactic structures similar to them in form - phrases or sentences), but are reproduced in it in a socially assigned stable ratio of semantic content and a certain lexical and grammatical composition. Semantic shifts in the meanings of lexical components, stability and reproducibility are interconnected universal and distinctive features of a phraseological unit - according to Shansky.

The structural and semantic properties of phraseological units that distinguish their types are formed, as a rule, in the process of rethinking the original combinations of words as a whole or at least one of the lexical components of the combination. In the first case, phraseological units are formed that have a continuous meaning (or the property of idiomaticity). A fused meaning can be figurative or ugly and is indecomposable into the meanings of their lexical components: to look through one's fingers, to see the sights, to laugh at chickens, to feel relieved from the heart. In the second, a phraseologically related meaning is formed in the rethought word, which can only rejoice in combination with a certain word or with a number of words, which leads to the formation of stable verbal complexes that have an analytical (dissected) meaning: white meat, golden youth, slave of passions (habits, fashion), come to a thought (to a conclusion, to a decision) [Shansky N.M., 1969].

V.M. Nikitin writes: "Phraseological units are not language phenomena, but style phenomena. They do not have their own nominative function" [11].

Among the phraseological units of the first kind, phraseological fusions are distinguished (their meanings are completely unmotivated in the modern vocabulary of the language): pour bullets, the curve will take out, on all peels, and phraseological units, in the meaning of which one can single out the meaning motivated by the meanings of the components, in their usual use: block the way, at full speed, dark forest. A distinctive feature of unity is figurativeness.

Phraseologisms, characterized by analytical meaning, are a special type of structural and semantic units of phraseological composition - phraseological combinations. These are phraseological turns in which there are words, both with free meaning and with phraseologically connected ones. A specific feature of words with a phraseologically related meaning is their lack of an independent sign function: with the semantic separation of such meanings of words, they are able to designate out of linguistic objects only in combination with other words that act as nominatively supporting components of these combinations of words (black bread, black market, black suit, black day). This property of them is manifested in the dependence of the choice of words with phraseologically related meanings on semantically key words in the process of constructing the lexico-grammatical composition of the sentence. Restrictions in choice are fixed by a norm that fixes the compatibility of words in their phraseologically related meanings with

certain words: in one word, a row of words or several rows, for example: overspending, the finger of fate, the son of the steppes (mountains), deep old age or deep night (autumn, winter), and combinations as a whole are characterized by limitations in the transformation of their lexical and grammatical structure. Words with phraseologically related meanings act as constant elements of phraseological combinations, they act in synonymous, antonymic and subject-thematic relationships only together with semantically key words for them. Phraseological combinations almost do not have homonymous free combinations of words [12].

N.M. Shansky also identifies the fourth type of phraseological units - phraseological expressions. These are phraseological phrases that are stable in their composition and use, which are not only semantically articulated, but also consist entirely of words with a free meaning. Phraseological expressions differ from phraseological combinations in that they do not contain words with phraseologically related meaning: All ages are submissive to love; They are afraid of wolves - do not go into the forest; wholesale and retail; seriously and for a long time; the process has begun; market economy. The words that form them cannot have synonyms. " Their hallmark is reproducibility. Phraseological expressions are divided into normative and communicative (correlated with a part of a sentence and with a sentence, respectively) [17].

Some supporters of the theory of complete equivalence consider phraseological units as lexical units that do not need a special, specific, unique classification, and which should be classified in the same way as

words are classified. Thus, all the specifics of phraseological units are reduced to nothing. The word, no matter how complex in terms of semantic structure, does not belong to the field of phraseology, it is an object of lexicography and lexicology.

Words and phraseological units are introduced into speech in finished form. This fact is given as one of the arguments in favor of the theory of complete equivalence. Introduction into speech in finished form is a shaky basis for the equivalence of a phraseological unit to a word, since reproduction in finished form is a characteristic feature of all units of the language, and it is inappropriate to consider them as equivalents of words. It is only important to take into account the characteristic features of reproducibility in the finished form, depending on the structural and semantic features of various units of the language. And in the structural and semantic sense, phraseology is a separate unit of language, much more complex than a word, and this affects its actualization in a written or oral context [8].

Phraseological semantics is closely related to lexical semantics, but, nevertheless, it has a number of characteristic features. The following are subject to consideration: types of meanings in the field of phraseology, phraseological rethinking, phraseological abstraction, the internal form of phraseological units, aspects of phraseological meaning. When analyzing the meaning of phraseological units, it is also important to isolate semes, semantic elements that are smaller than one or another aspect of phraseological meaning. The semantic structure of phraseological units is wider than its meaning, since it is not limited to significative, denotative and

connotative aspects, but is also determined by the construction of the entire education as a whole, the type of its grammatical meaning, for example, number or case, monosemantic or polysemantic, as well as systemic language and speech connections.

In linguistics, semantics occupies a very special place, since, on the one hand, it permeates all language levels, and on the other hand, it connects linguistics with such sciences as philosophy, logic, psychology, semiotics, etc. The term "semantics" exists within different sciences and under this is understood every time in its own way. Its correct use presupposes a fairly wide acquaintance with these sciences and taking into account the peculiarities of philosophical, logical and other semantics [10]

Semantics (from the Greek *semaino* - to mean and *semanticos* - meaning) is the science of meaning. It is impossible to say exactly when it was born, as well as about many other sciences. Often the origins of semantics are found in ancient Greek philosophy. Thus, in H. Kronasser, his essay on the history of semantics begins with the Sophists and Plato, followed by Aristotle. However, semantic ideas can also be seen in Chinese philosophy (Mohism, Mingjia, and other schools). H. Kronasser connects the beginning of semantics as an independent discipline with the appearance of the works of the English philosopher J. Locke and dates back to the middle of the 17th century. The formation of linguistic semantics proper, by all accounts, dates back to the 19th century. Semantics is an integral part not only of linguistics, but also of philosophy, logic and semiotics.

In linguistics, semantics is interpreted in two different senses. Firstly, this term denotes the meaning of some linguistic sign as a whole. In such combinations as the semantics of a word, the semantics of a sentence, it is close to the term "meaning", although with a narrower scope of consumption.

Secondly, the term "semantics" is used as the name of the science that studies semantics in the first sense [7].

The semantic structure of words belonging to the same lexical and grammatical category, and the semantic structure of phraseological units corresponding to them, for example, nouns - substantive phraseological units, never completely coincide. This is proved by the analysis of non-coinciding components of the semantic structures of the above formations.

The semantic structure of phraseological fusions and unities does not coincide. Each type of phraseological unit has its own semantic features, for example, unmotivated and motivated meanings. But they also have some common features: one or another degree of rethinking of the meaning and phraseological abstraction, based on the separate formation of the whole and the integral formation of the parts within the framework of the above phraseological structures. The literal meaning of the PU components, as well as the literal or rethought meaning of its prototype, is an integral part of the semantic structure of a motivated phraseological unit.

The semantic structure of the word is very complex. Although phraseological units are inferior to words in terms of polysemy, the semantic structure of phraseological units, with the exception of phraseomatisms, is also extremely complex. This is due to the

rethought nature of the phraseological meaning, the interweaving of various aspects in it, the separate design of phraseological units and the complexity of their structure, the range of which is very significant and covers turns from one-vertex phraseological units to complex sentences. As a result, in various works, a phraseological unit is called a compound sign, a mega-sign or a combination of dictionary signs, a composite or composite analytical sign, a separate sign, etc.

Cognition embraces the dialectic of the universal and the individual. In phraseology, this regularity is manifested in the fact that phraseological units can denote both general concepts characteristic of a given class of objects, and single concepts closely related to them [8].

Phraseological units, or phraseological units, reflect the national specificity of the language, its identity. The phraseology captures the rich historical experience of the people, it reflects ideas related to work, life and culture of people. The study of phraseology is a necessary link in the acquisition of the language, in improving the culture of speech. The correct and appropriate use of phraseological units gives speech a unique originality, special expressiveness, accuracy, imagery.

During our research, we came to the following conclusions:

- Phraseologism - a stable phrase that performs the function of a separate word, the meaning of which is not derived from the meanings of their constituent components. Phraseological units can be divided into three main types of phraseological units, which were called "splicing phraseology", "unity phraseology", "combination phraseology".

- Phraseologism - a turnover reproduced in speech, built on the model of coordinating or subordinating phrases, having a holistic meaning and combined with the word.
- Phraseologism is endowed with a number of essential, defining features: reproducibility, stability, semantic integrity of meaning, dismemberment of its composition, openness (openness) of the structure.
- Sources of origin of phraseological units in modern English are very diverse. A.V. Kunin, who devoted a special monograph to this issue, divides English phraseological units according to their origin into three main groups:

- 1) native English,
 - 2) borrowed from foreign languages and
 - 3) borrowed from American English.
 - Most of the English and Russian phraseological units associated with the vocabulary of "parts of the body" are the same in meaning and figurativeness.
- This work aroused great interest in us and enriched our vocabulary, taught us how to build logical connections between different meanings of the same word, introduced us to a large number of interesting English phraseological phrases, and broadened our horizons.

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